

ISic0114

I.Sicily inscription 0114

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

Photographed 2018-07-10

Last Change

2020-12-10 - Jonathan Prag edited file from publication and photograph

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Original details of discovery not recorded; first attested in Termini

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 102

Physical Description

A thick, pinkish limestone plaque, intact on all sides but with the face damaged on the left, upper and right edges (later re-working?), and the lower right corner

Dimensions

Height 21 cm

Width 29.5 cm

Depth 9 cm

Layout

Three lines of Latin text, approximately centred and with a vacat below

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat thinly cut letters mostly without substantial serifs/terminations to the strokes. Letters are somewhat irregular both in height and width. A has horizontal bar which does not fully intersect the diagonals; B has rounded eyes, not closed, and the upper is smaller; E has equal horizontal strokes; G has vertical tail stroke; O is variable in dimensions; P has rounded open head; R is lcosd, with full tail. Small triangular interpunct in line 1.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 32-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. P(ublio) · Antonio P(ublio) [(i)bert(o)]
2. Psorioni
3. ergolabo

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To Publius Antonius Psorion, (freedman?) of Publius, a contractor.

Commentary

The term 'ergolabus', a transliteration of the Greek ἐργόλαβος is possibly unique in Latin (instead of redemptor); the Greek term is occasionally attested.

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Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7363 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650797>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 32

Rizzo, F.P. 1989. *La menzione del lavoro nelle epigrafi della Sicilia antica: per una storia della mentalità. Seia.* Palermo. At 73 no.43

Manganaro, G. 1988. *La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49 n.244

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